

Composition and Stability of the Chelates of Trivalent Gallium, Indium, and Thallium with 3,3'-Bis-*NN'*-di-(carboxymethyl)aminomethyl-*o*-cresol Sulphonphthalein (Xylenol Orange)

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Detailed studies on the composition and stability of the metal chelates¹ of trivalent gallium, indium, and thallium with Xylenol orange, that is, 3,3'-bis-*NN'*-di-(carboxymethyl)aminomethyl-*o*-cresol sulphophthalein (DCAC) have been made. All the chelates have the composition of 1 : 1.

Ishiwatari *et al.*² made some observations on the indium chelate only in connection with the spectrophotometric determination of indium with Xylenol orange. Chelates of gallium, indium, and thallium with DCAC have been studied in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of DCAC (B.D.H. indicator) were prepared by dissolving known amounts of the reagent in 10% aqueous ethanol. Solutions of gallium, indium, and thallium trichlorides in HCl (B.D.H. AnalaR), using Johnson, Matthey & Co. samples, were prepared and standardised.

Absorbance measurements were made with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer at 25°, using 1 cm thickness of the solutions as described earlier³.

Hydrogen-ion concentrations were measured with a Leeds and Northrup pH indicator. All experiments were performed at 25°. The total volume of all the mixtures, prepared for the measurements, was kept at 25 ml. The individual solutions and mixtures were adjusted to pH 4.0 by addition of HCl or NaOH and stored at 25° ± 0.01° for about 1 hr. before use. Added electrolytes in the solution produced coagulation of the lake and hence constant ionic strength could not be maintained.

The compositions of the chelates were determined by (i) the method of continued variations⁴, (ii) the mole-ratio method⁵, and (iii) the slope-ratio method⁶.

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DISCUSSION

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁷ was used for determination of the nature of the complexes formed in solution. The reagent alone showed a maximum absorption at 440 m μ at pH 4.0, but mixtures containing varying proportions of M (metal: Ga, In, Tl) and DCAC (0:1.0, 1:0.5, 1:1.0, 1:2.0, 1:3.0, 1:4.0) had λ_{max} at 560 m μ in the case of gallium and indium and at 590 m μ in the case of thallium, indicating formation of only one chelate in solution under the conditions of study. The chelates have the same λ_{max} at pH range 2.8-0.5 in the case of Ga-DCAC, 3.0-0.5 in In-DCAC, and 3.0-6.5 in Tl-DCAC, showing the pH range of the stability of the chelates.

The colour formation is instantaneous and the absorbance values remain constant even up to 72 hr. No significant change occurs when the order of the addition of the reactants is altered.

The gallium-, indium-, and thallium-DCAC chelates have the composition of 1:1 at pH 4.0 as determined by the method of continued variations (Fig. 1-3). Above conclusions have been supported by the results obtained by the mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods (Fig. not shown).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Evaluation of the Stability Constants

The apparent stability constants, K , under the conditions mentioned, were calculated from the absorbance data using (i) the modified method of Anderson *et al.*⁸ as adopted by Dey *et al.*⁹, (ii) the mole-ratio method as suggested by Harvey and Manning⁹, (iii) the method of continued variations⁴, and (iv) through calculation of the molecular extinction coefficients.

The values of $\log K$, as obtained by four different methods, are recorded in Table I. The values of the change in free energy of formation (ΔG°)^{*} have also been calculated.

* $\Delta G^\circ = RT \log K$.

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8. *Ibid.*, 1948, 70, 1195; 1949, 71, 900, 912.

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TABLE I

Apparent stability constants ($\log K$) of the chelates.
 $pH = 4.0$.

Method.	$\log K$.	ΔG° at 25° (kcal.).	$\log K$.	ΔG° at 25° (kcal.).	$\log K$.	ΔG° at 25° (kcal.).
	A. Ga (III)—DCAC.		B. In (III)—DCAC.		C. Tl (III)—DCAC.	
(i)	4.8 ± 0.1	-6.6 ± 0.1	5.2 ± 0.1	-7.2 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.0	-6.5 ± 0.0
(ii)	4.8 ± 0.0	-6.6 ± 0.0	5.2 ± 0.0	-7.2 ± 0.1	4.8 ± 0.0	-6.6 ± 0.0
(iii)	4.8 ± 0.0	-6.6 ± 0.2	4.9 ± 0.0	-6.7 ± 0.2	4.8 ± 0.0	-6.7 ± 0.0
(iv)	4.8 ± 0.2	-6.6 ± 0.2	5.0 ± 0.2	-7.7 ± 0.2	5.1 ± 0.1	-7.0 ± 0.2

Structure of the Chelates

The study of absorption spectra of DCAC solutions at various pH s indicates that the colour of the ligand changes with variations in the H^+ -ion concentrations of the media. This is indicated by the shifts in the region of maximum absorption. Several different ionic transformations of the dye in solution have been observed which support the results reported by Behak and Korbl¹⁰. From the change in colour of the ligand with progressive increase in the pH , it is possible to throw light on the stepwise dissociation of the ligand. DCAC in a strongly acidic medium forms a zwitter ion indicated by H_7DCAC^+ ; through the deprotonation of the sulphonate group H_6DCAC^0 is formed. It has been assumed that under these conditions, the ionisation of the sulphonate group is complete. Finally, with decrease in acidity, the H^+ of the zwitter ion is removed and the structure H_5DCAC^{2-} is formed. This product further ionises. The dissociation corresponds to the ionisation of the four carboxylic hydrogens and finally to that of the phenolic oxygen.

As the chelates have the composition of 1:1, the chelation takes place between two carboxylic oxygens by the replacement of two hydrogens and through the nitrogen, forming two 5-membered rings as:

The chelates have been found to be anionic since it is completely adsorbed by anion-exchange resin, Amberlite IR-15(OH). It may be recalled that the λ_{max} of the chelates lies between 580 and 590m μ in all the cases, suggesting that the colour resembles that of the reagent in an alkaline medium when all the carboxylic hydrogens are ionised. Hence it

appears that in the metal chelates of gallium, indium, and thallium also, all the carboxylic groups remain ionised. This explains that the chelates have a colour resembling that of the reagent alone with all the carboxylic groups ionised and also shows their anionic nature. The present work, however, is unable to throw further light on the structure and the above views are purely tentative.

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